

COMBINED ASCORBIC ACID IN PLANT FOODSTUFFS. PART I.

BY JATINDRA CHANDRA PAL AND B. C. GUHA.

Evidence has been presented to indicate the presence of combined ascorbic acid, "ascorbigen", in several plant tissues. It can be extracted from cabbage by suitable means.

The state in which ascorbic acid is present in certain natural foodstuffs has been the subject of some discussion. Ahmad (*Nature*, 1935, **136**, 797) observed an increase in the ascorbic acid value of cabbage on cooking. A similar increase in cauliflower, carrots, turnips, beets and potatoes on boiling with water was observed by McHenry and Graham (*Nature*, 1935, **135**, 871), who considered that the increase was due to the liberation of ascorbic acid from a combined form, possibly an ester. Van Eekelen (*Nature*, 1935, **136**, 144), working with potatoes, concluded, however, that the observed increase in ascorbic acid value was not due to any such liberation of free ascorbic acid from bound ascorbic acid, but was to be ascribed to the destruction of ascorbic acid oxidase, present in the natural substances, by boiling. Since then Reedman and McHenry (*Biochem. J.*, 1938, **32**, 85) and Scarborough and Stewart (*Biochem. J.*, 1937, **31**, 2232) have presented evidence supporting the presence of combined ascorbic acid in plant tissues and in urine respectively.

The following experiments were planned in order to investigate this problem, preliminary reports of which have been published elsewhere (Guha and Pal, *Nature*, 1936, **137**, 946 ; 1937, **139**, 844). It was considered that solvents like absolute alcohol and ether, which might perhaps extract the combined ascorbic acid from cabbage, would be unlikely to extract the enzyme, ascorbic acid oxidase, and therefore, the behaviour of such extracts to heat should be studied. Secondly, assuming that absolute alcohol would extract some of the oxidase, it was of interest to investigate if exposure of such extracts to a temperature of 36°, which was very unlikely to destroy the enzyme, would cause any increase in ascorbic acid value. Thirdly, the ethereal extract of cabbage, which gave an increased ascorbic acid value on heating, was itself examined and found devoid of ascorbic acid oxidase. Fourthly, it was considered that treatment of the cabbage suspensions and extracts with hydrogen sulphide in the hot and cold conditions should throw light on this question. Whatever dehydroascorbic acid may be formed by the action of the oxidase, all of it will be readily

reduced by hydrogen sulphide in the cold and hence any difference between the results obtained in the hot and cold states is likely to be due to the splitting up of combined ascorbic acid by heat.

The titrations were carried out against the indophenol reagent according to the usual titrimetric method and also in several cases by van Eekelen's procedure or after treatment with formaldehyde in order to eliminate possible interfering substances. All the results indicate that a part of the ascorbic acid present in several foodstuffs investigated is present in the combined form, and further, it has been possible to extract this substance from cabbage in a state practically free from ascorbic acid and attempts are being made to isolate this substance. We have called this combined ascorbic acid, from which ascorbic acid is released on heating, 'ascorbigen' for convenience and brevity.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

I. The Ascorbic Acid Values of Cabbage Extracted in Different Ways.

In these experiments titrations were carried out by the usual titrimetric method.

(A) Cabbage was obtained from the local market, cut up as finely as possible from three different cabbages and thoroughly mixed.

(i) 10 G. were taken, ground well in a mortar with sea-sand under 20% trichloroacetic acid and, after addition of water, the mixture was centrifuged. The centrifugate was made up to 100 c.c. and its ascorbic acid content estimated (Table I A, column i).

(ii) Cabbage (10 g.) from the above sample was boiled with water for 5 minutes in air and cooled under the tap; the mixture was extracted with trichloroacetic acid and centrifuged and ascorbic acid was estimated as above (Table I A, column ii).

(iii) The experiment was repeated as under (ii), boiling being carried out in an atmosphere of nitrogen for 5 minutes (Table I A, column iii).

It will be seen from Table I A, which gives results of three different sets of experiments, that the average percentage increases by heating cabbage for 5 minutes in air are 26.5, and for 5 minutes in nitrogen 40.6.

The figures for ascorbic acid would have been higher, if the cabbages, without being cut into pieces previously, had been ground up under trichloroacetic acid, as the oxidase would have been immediately destroyed by the acid. But in our experiments, in order to ensure sampling and comparability of results, the cabbage was first cut into pieces and then divided into different portions to be variously treated. This allowed the

oxidase some time to act on the ascorbic acid. The conditions of experiment were, however, identical and the effect of heat is noticeable.

TABLE IA.

Case.	Ascorbic acid per 100 g. of cabbage treated as in		
	(i). Extracted with trichloroacetic acid without any previous treatment.	(ii). Boiled for 5 minutes in air and then extracted.	(iii). Boiled for 5 minutes in nitrogen and then extracted.
1	14.28 mg.	15.38 mg.	18.11 mg.
2	12.27	14.28	15.99
3	14.28	22.22	23.53

(B). In this set of experiments van Eekelen's method and formaldehyde treatment were also used for the removal of any possible interfering substances. Sampled cabbage was divided into 10 g. portions. One lot of 10 g. was extracted in the usual way by grinding well with sea-sand in a mortar and under 20% trichloroacetic acid; the centrifugate was made up to 100 c.c. and ascorbic acid was estimated in different portions of it by the following methods.

(i) Ascorbic acid was estimated by titrating against the indophenol reagent (Table I B, column *i*).

(ii) Ascorbic acid was estimated by titrating against the indophenol reagent after adding 1 c.c. of *M*-formaldehyde solution to the dye (Table I B, column *ii*).

(iii) The extract was treated first by the mercuric acetate method of van Eekelen, and then the ascorbic acid content was estimated by the indophenol reagent (Table I B, column *iii*).

Another lot of 10 g. of cabbage from the above sample was heated with water in an atmosphere of nitrogen for 4 minutes, cooled under the tap and ground well with trichloroacetic acid, the ascorbic acid was extracted in the usual way and the volume of the centrifugate made up to 100 c.c. Three different portions of this were estimated by the different methods mentioned above (Table I B, columns *iv*, *v*, *vi*).

Table I B, which gives results of three different sets of experiments, shows that the average percentage increases by heating cabbage for 4 minutes in nitrogen are 201.4 by the ordinary method, 204.1 by the formaldehyde method and 153.9 by van Eekelen's method. This shows strikingly that, whichever the method of estimation employed, there is a remarkable increase in the ascorbic acid value after boiling in nitrogen.

TABLE IB.

(Figures are given in mg. of ascorbic acid per 100 g. of cabbage)

Case	Trichloroacetic acid extract			Boiled in N ₂ for 4 minutes and then extracted with trichloroacetic acid		
	(i). By ordinary titration.	(ii). By adding 1 c.c. M-HCHO to the dye.	(iii). By van Eekelen's method.	(iv). By ordinary titration	(v). By adding 1 c.c. M-HCHO to the dye.	(vi). By van Eekelen's method.
1	12.65	12.50	10.30	45.45	45.45	28.87
2	17.42	17.24	15.21	43.47	43.47	34.87
3	15.86	15.86	12.63	47.06	47.06	32.90

(C) Sampled cabbage (10 g.) was ground well in a mortar with sea-sand under trichloroacetic acid and ascorbic acid was extracted by centrifuging with water. The extract was divided into two portions.

(i) One portion was titrated without heating (Table Ic, column i).

(ii) The other portion was heated on a boiling water-bath for 4 minutes in an atmosphere of nitrogen under reflux condenser, cooled under the tap and then the ascorbic acid was estimated (Table Ic, column ii.)

It will be seen from Table Ic that the ascorbic acid content of the trichloroacetic acid extract of cabbage does not increase on heating in nitrogen, which might perhaps indicate that trichloroacetic acid does not extract much of the bound ascorbic acid or that the hot acid has a destructive action on it (*vide* Sec. VIII).

TABLE IC.

(Figures are given in mg. of ascorbic acid per 100 g. of cabbage.)

Case	Trichloroacetic acid extract	
	(i)	(ii). Trichloroacetic acid extract heated in N ₂ for 4 minutes
1	20.83	20.56
2	12.50	8.17
3	17.76	15.90

II. Extraction of Cabbage with Absolute Alcohol.

Sampled cabbage (50 g.) was ground well with anhydrous sodium sulphate (about 200 g. of the sulphate were required). This was taken in a 500 c.c. flask and shaken with absolute alcohol in 2 or 3 instalments (75 c.c. of absolute alcohol each time) and filtered through Buchner funnel. The filtrates were collected and the final volume was determined, to which half its volume of distilled water was added.

Aliquot portions were taken in different conical flasks. One was titrated against the indophenol reagent in the cold, and others were heated at different temperatures and for different periods, some in air and the remaining in an atmosphere of nitrogen, all under reflux. condenser, cooled under the tap and were titrated with the indophenol reagent (Table II). The alcoholic extract, which was slightly coloured, was in each case diluted with half its volume of water before titration so as to diminish the intensity of colour.

As will be seen from the table, the average percentage increases are 48.6 by heating the extract on a boiling water-bath for 4 minutes in air, 83.3 by heating similarly for 4 minutes in an atmosphere of nitrogen and 35.0 by heating at 40° for 10 minutes in an atmosphere of nitrogen.

TABLE II.

Case.	Titrated without heating.		Heating in air		Heating in nitrogen		
	Ascorbic acid per 100 g. of substance.	Time of heating.	Condition of heating	Ascorbic acid per 100 g. of substance.	Time of heating.	Condition of heating.	Ascorbic acid per 100 g. of substance.
1	0.48 mg.	4 min.	On boiling water-bath	0.75 mg.	4 min.	On boiling water-bath	0.82 mg.
2	0.98	4	Do	1.46	4	Do	1.77
3	0.17	4	36°	0.17	4	36°	0.18
					10	36°	0.19
4	0.72	4	On boiling water-bath	1.20	10	40°	1.17
					4	On boiling water-bath	1.86
5	6.88	4	Do	8.80	10	40°	9.20
					4	On boiling water-bath	9.90
6	6.91	4	Do	9.60	10	40°	7.28
					4	On boiling water-bath	12.55
7	8.92	4	Do	13.80	10	40°	12.36
					4	On boiling water-bath	15.92

III. Extraction of Cabbage with Ether.

Sampled cabbage (50 g.) was ground well with anhydrous sodium sulphate as under Section II, and extracted with ether in 2 or 3 instalments using 75 c.c. of ether each time and filtered through Buchner funnel. The collected filtrate was evaporated by means of a fan. The cream-like residue was taken up in water and the insoluble substance filtered off. The filtrate was made up to a definite volume, one portion of which

was titrated in the cold. Other portions were heated at different temperatures and for different periods in an atmosphere of nitrogen under reflux condenser, cooled and then the ascorbic acid content was determined (Table III).

These results show that free ascorbic acid is not extracted from cabbage by ether under anhydrous conditions and that the ethereal extract, after treatment with water and heating on a boiling water-bath in nitrogen, produces free ascorbic acid invariably, while at 40° increase is observed in several cases. It is apparent that ether extracts some ascorbigen from cabbage.

TABLE III.

Case.	Titrated without heating.		Heating in nitrogen	
	Ascorbic acid per 100 g. of substance.	Time of heating.	Condition of heating.	Ascorbic acid per 100 g. of substance.
1	0 mg.	4 min.	On boiling water-bath	0.70 mg.
2	0	10	40°	0.52
		4	On boiling water-bath	0.76
3	0	10	40°	0.48
		4	On boiling water-bath	0.74
4	0	10	40°	No appreciable change
		4	On boiling water-bath	2.45 mg.
5	0	10	40°	No appreciable change
		4	On boiling water-bath	1.29 mg.
6	0	30	40°	No appreciable change
		60	40°	Do

IV. Testing of the Ethereal Extract of Cabbage for Ascorbic Acid Oxidase.

A. Sampled cabbage (50 g.) was extracted with ether in presence of anhydrous sodium sulphate as under Section III. The ethereal extract was evaporated by means of a fan, the residue was taken to solution in an acetate buffer of p_H 5.5 (see Tauber, Kleiner and Mishkind, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1935, 110, 211), filtered, and the filtrate was made up to a definite volume with the above buffer solution.

B. 2 G. of the above cabbage sample were ground well in a mortar with sand and extracted with buffer of p_H 5.5. The total volume was made up to a definite volume with the buffer.

C. An approximately known weight of pure ascorbic acid was made into a solution with buffer of p_H 5.5 and made up to a definite volume with the buffer.

For testing of the ethereal extract of cabbage for ascorbic acid oxidase, the following experiments were arranged, the total volume in each case being made up to 20 c.c. with buffer of p_H 5.5.

(a) 2 C.c. of ethereal extract (A) + 14 c.c. of ascorbic acid solution (C) + 4 c.c. of buffer.

(b) 2 C.c. of ethereal extract (A) + 18 c.c. of buffer.

(c) 14 C.c. of ascorbic acid solution (C) + 6 c.c. of buffer.

(d) 14 C.c. of ascorbic acid solution (C) + 2 c.c. of aqueous extract (B) + 4 c.c. of buffer.

(e) 2 C.c. of ethereal extract (A) + 18 c.c. of buffer.

(a), (b), (c) and (d) were all taken in similarly corked conical flasks and incubated in a thermostat at 38° for 60 minutes, while (e) was heated on a boiling water-bath under reflux in nitrogen for 4 minutes. The total ascorbic acid contents of all these were estimated and are given in Table IV. The fact that figures under (a) are greater than the sums of the figures under (b) and (c) shows the absence of ascorbic acid oxidase in the ethereal extract and shows, further, that under these conditions also part of the ascorbigen of the ethereal extract splits producing free ascorbic acid. The figures under (d) show the presence of the oxidase in the aqueous extract of cabbage, while figures under (e) show that heating in nitrogen releases a certain amount of ascorbic acid from the ethereal extract, as has been shown in the previous section.

TABLE IV.

Figures are given in mg. ascorbic acid.

Case.	(a).	(b).	(c).	(d).	(e).
1	7.27	0.010	6.66	—	0.024
2	2.10	0.023	2.00	0.38	0.033
3	0.47	0.007	0.43	0.12	0.024

V. *Extraction of Germinated Mung (Phaseolus Mungo) in Different Ways.*

Kancha mung (5 g.) was kept for germination in a petri-dish with water. The seeds were allowed to germinate for 48 hours. During this period water was added from time to time in small quantities in order to keep them moist. Excess of water was always avoided to prevent putrefaction of the seeds.

A. *Aqueous Extract of the Germinated Mung.*

The germinated seeds were taken in a mortar, ground well with sea-sand and extracted with water. The total volume of the centrifugate was made up to 100 c.c., which was divided into two portions (a) and (b).

(a) This portion was again divided into the following 3 parts.

(i) Ascorbic acid was estimated in one part by the indophenol reagent (Table VA, column i).

(ii) Ascorbic acid was estimated by the above method, after adding 1 c.c. of *M*-formaldehyde solution to the dye (Table VA, column ii).

(iii) The solution was first treated by the mercuricacetate method of van Eekelen, and then the ascorbic acid content was estimated (Table VA, column iii).

(b) This solution was heated on a boiling water-bath for 4 minutes in an atmosphere of nitrogen under reflux condenser, cooled under the tap and was divided into 3 parts, which were estimated by the different methods, mentioned above (Table VA, columns *iv*, *v* and *vi*).

The results show an increase of the ascorbic acid value on heating in nitrogen, as estimated by all these three methods.

B. *Alcoholic Extract of the Germinated Mung.*

The germinated *mung* was taken in a mortar, ground well with anhydrous sodium sulphate and extracted with absolute alcohol as under Section II. The alcoholic solution was treated with half its volume of distilled water. One portion of this was titrated in the cold (Table VB, column *i*). Another portion was heated on a boiling water-bath for 4 minutes in an atmosphere of nitrogen under reflux condenser, cooled under the tap, and then titrated (Table VB, column *ii*).

C. *Ether Extract of Germinated Mung.*

The germinated *mung* was ground in a mortar and extracted with ether in presence of anhydrous sodium sulphate as under Section III. The ethereal extract was dried by means of a fan, the residue taken into solution, filtered and the filtrate was made up to a known volume. This was divided into two portions, one portion was titrated in the cold (Table Vc, column *i*) and the other portion was heated on a boiling water-bath for 4 minutes in nitrogen under reflux condenser, cooled and then titrated (Table Vc). The values are calculated on the basis of the dry weight of the seeds.

TABLE VA.

Aqueous extract of germinated mung.

Figures are given in mg. ascorbic acid per g. of dry *mung*.

Case.	Cold aqueous extract of germinated <i>mung</i> .			Aqueous extract of germinated <i>mung</i> heated in nitrogen,		
	(i) Ordinary titration.	(ii). Titration in presence of M. formaldehyde.	(iii). Treatment by van Eckelen's method	(iv). Ordinary titration.	(v). Titration in presence of M. formaldehyde.	(vi). Treatment by van Eckelen's method.
1	10.00	10.00	7.42	12.50	12.30	9.04
2	12.12	12.12	10.43	13.33	13.33	11.90
3	9.09	9.09	6.40	12.50	12.30	9.30
4	6.45	6.45	4.34	8.88	8.79	6.23
5	6.15	6.10	4.44	8.69	8.69	6.54

TABLE VB.

Alcoholic extract of germinated mung.

Case	(i) Ascorbic acid per 100 g. of dry <i>mung</i> before heating in nitrogen.	(ii) Ascorbic acid per 100 g. of dry <i>mung</i> after heating in nitrogen.
1	2.25 mg.	2.90 mg.
2	2.50	2.72
5	2.68	2.93

TABLE VC.

Ethereal extract of germinated mung.

Case.	(i) Ascorbic acid per 100 g. of dry <i>mung</i> before heating in nitrogen	(ii) Ascorbic acid per 100 g. of dry <i>mung</i> after heating in nitrogen.
1	0 mg.	1.12 mg.
2	0	1.30
2	0	1.41

VI. Extraction of "Bel" (*Aegle Marmelos*) with Absolute Alcohol and Ether.

A. *Extraction of Bel with Absolute Alcohol.*—50 G. of *bel* sampled from 3 different fruits, were ground well with anhydrous sodium sulphate and extracted with absolute alcohol as under Section II. The alcoholic extract was treated with half its volume of distilled water and divided into aliquots. One portion was titrated in the cold and the others were titrated after heating at different temperatures and for different periods of time in an atmosphere of nitrogen under reflux condenser (Table VIA).

TABLE VIA.

Alcoholic extract of bel.

Case.	Titrated without heating.		Titrated after heating in nitrogen.	
	Ascorbic acid per 100 g. of substance.	Time of heating.	Condition of heating.	Ascorbic acid per 100 g. of substance.
1	9.85 mg.	10 min.	40°	11.50 mg.
		4	On boiling water-bath	12.17
2	7.71	30	40°	9.07
		4	On boiling water-bath	8.07
3	4.30	30	40°	4.60
		4	On boiling water-bath	4.67

B. *Extraction of Bel with Ether.*—50 G. of sampled *bel* were ground well with anhydrous sodium sulphate and extracted with ether as under Section III. The ethereal extract was air-dried, the residue was taken in solution, filtered and the filtrate was made up to a definite volume. The solution was divided into aliquots; one portion was titrated in the cold and the others were heated at different temperatures and for different periods of time in an atmosphere of nitrogen under reflux condenser, cooled under the tap and then titrated (Table VIB).

TABLE VIB.

Ethereal extract of bel,

Case.	Titrated without heating.		Titrated after heating in nitrogen.	
	Ascorbic acid per 100 g. of substance.	Time of heating.	Condition of heating.	Ascorbic acid per 100 g. of substance.
1	0 mg.	60 min.	40°	No appreciable change
		4	On boiling water-bath	0.27 mg.
2	0	4	water-bath	0.24
		60	40°	No appreciable change

VII. Extraction of Mango with Absolute Alcohol.

Sampled mango (25 g.) was ground well with anhydrous sodium sulphate and extracted with absolute alcohol as under Section II. The volume of the alcoholic extract was measured and diluted with half its volume of distilled water. This was titrated both in the cold and after heating at different

temperatures and for different periods of time under reflux condenser in an atmosphere of nitrogen (Table VII).

Both green and ripe mangoes were used. But in no case was ascorbigen found to be present.

TABLE VII.

Case.	Titrated without heating.		Titrated after heating in nitrogen.	
	Ascorbic acid per 100 g. of substance.	Time of heating.	Condition of heating.	Ascorbic acid per 100 g. of substance.
1 (Ripe)	7.85 mg.	60 min. 4	40° On boiling water-bath	6.53 mg. 5.68
2 (Green)	18.62	60 4	40° On boiling water-bath	12.67 12.73

VIII. *The Behaviour of the Aqueous Extract of Cabbage to Acids.*

Sampled cabbage (10 g.) was ground well with sea-sand and extracted with water and centrifuged. The clear liquid after centrifuging was diluted to a definite volume. The solution was then kept in six similar conical flasks in aliquot portions.

(a) This was titrated as such.

(b) This was allowed to stand for 1 hour at room temperature (31°) and then ascorbic acid was estimated.

(c) This was made 0.2% acid (equivalent to the hydrochloric acid concentration in gastric juice) with hydrochloric acid, allowed to stand for 1 hour at room temperature (31°), and then ascorbic acid was estimated.

(d) This was heated in an atmosphere of nitrogen on a boiling water-bath for 4 minutes under reflux condenser, cooled and then ascorbic acid was estimated.

(e) This was made 0.2% acid with hydrochloric acid, heated in nitrogen on a boiling water-bath for 4 minutes under reflux, cooled and then ascorbic acid was estimated.

(f) This was made 0.25% acid with trichloroacetic acid, heated in an atmosphere of nitrogen on a boiling water-bath for 4 minutes under reflux, cooled and then ascorbic acid was estimated.

The results are given in Table VIII.

The comparative values under (a), (b) and (c) indicate that 0.2% acid solution (with HCl) causes a considerable splitting up of ascorbigen. The values under (d), (e) and (f) seem to indicate that heating in nitrogen at the normal p_H of the cabbage extract produces a greater increase in

ascorbic acid value than if the heating is carried out in presence of hydrochloric or trichloroacetic acid. Of these two acids again, the former appears to give a larger yield of free ascorbic acid.

TABLE VIII.

Figures are given in mg. of ascorbic acid per 100 g. of cabbage.

Case.	(a).	(b).	(c).	(d).	(e).	(f).
1	2.45	2.02	4.04	9.30	7.54	4.27
2	1.69	1.30	2.70	5.88	4.87	2.79
3	2.33	2.01	3.68	8.77	7.14	4.06

IX. Rate of Splitting of Ascorbigen in the Alcoholic Extract of Cabbage.

Sampled cabbage (50 g.) was ground well with anhydrous sodium sulphate in a mortar and extracted with absolute alcohol as under Section II. The volume of the alcoholic extract was measured and diluted with half its volume of distilled water. The solution was taken in a flask and incubated at 36° in a thermostat. Titrations were made at intervals of 5, 10, 20, 30 and 60 minutes by taking out aliquot portions (20 c.c.) from the flask.

The values are given in Table IX, which show that ascorbigen splits up progressively at 36° throughout 60 minutes.

TABLE IX.

Rate of splitting of ascorbigen in the alcoholic extract of cabbage.

Incubation of 36° for	Ascorbic acid per 100 g. of substance		
	Case 1.	Case 2.	Case 3.
0 min.	0.88 mg.	0.89	0.65
5	0.90	0.97	0.68
10	0.95	1.06	0.71
20	1.07	1.20	0.75
30	1.12	1.31	0.80
60	1.22	1.40	0.98

X. Behaviour of Cabbage Suspensions and Extracts to H₂S in the hot and cold Conditions.

(a) Two equal portions (10 g.) of sampled disintegrated cabbage were taken in suspension in water (50 c.c.). Sulphuretted hydrogen was passed for 45 minutes at room temperature (25°) into one portion. The other portion was

treated with H_2S for 30 minutes at room temperature and then the suspension was heated under reflux on a boiling water-bath for 15 minutes while H_2S was being passed. H_2S was removed completely from both the flasks by a current of N_2 and both suspensions were extracted with trichloroacetic acid and titrated in the ordinary way.

(b) Aqueous and alcoholic extracts of cabbage were treated with H_2S as under (a). Results are given in Table X.

TABLE X.

Figures are given in mg. of ascorbic acid per 100 g. of material.

Aq suspensions of cabbage.		Aq. extracts of cabbage.		Alcoholic extracts of cabbage.	
Effect of H_2S at 25°.		Effect of H_2S at 25°.		Effect of H_2S at 25°.	
	on boiling water-bath.		on boiling water-bath.		on boiling water-bath.
64.5	72.7	40.0	49.5	12.3	20.3
67.0	73.0	34.6	41.6	9.5	15.0
67.8	81.7	38.5	45.2	21.7	35.3
62.5	71.6	40.0	47.2	24.0	30.0
64.0	73.8				

In all cases, it will be seen, there is a difference between the effect of H_2S in the hot and cold conditions. Comparing Table X with Table IA, it will be seen that the values even for the cold H_2S treatment in Table X are much higher than in Table IA, the reason being that in Table IA the oxidase had time to act before extraction, while in Table X whatever dehydroascorbic acid was formed by the oxidase was reduced back to ascorbic acid by H_2S .

DISCUSSION.

The foregoing experiments indicate that part of the total ascorbic acid in such widely different plant foodstuffs as the cabbage, germinated mung (*Phaseolus mungo*) and the Indian fruit bel (*Aegle marmelos*) is present in a combined form, from which the free vitamin can be released by heating. The conclusion that this rise in ascorbic acid value on heating cannot be caused solely by the thermal destruction of ascorbic acid oxidase, as has been supposed by van Eekelen, is based on the following considerations: (1) the extract of cabbage with absolute alcohol gives a greatly increased value for ascorbic acid not merely on being heated on a boiling water-bath but also by exposure to a temperature of 36° or 40° for 10 minutes in an atmosphere of nitrogen (Section II). This

procedure is not likely to inactivate the ascorbic acid oxidase, even assuming that the enzyme comes out in the extraction with absolute alcohol.

(2) An extract of cabbage was obtained with dry ether, which showed no dye-reducing power as such but gave an increased value for ascorbic acid on being heated on a boiling water bath in an atmosphere of nitrogen (Section III). Ether would hardly be expected to extract the enzyme.

(3) The ethereal extract of cabbage was directly tested and found to be devoid of the oxidase (Section IV).

(4) Similar results were obtained also when ascorbic acid was estimated by van Eekelen's method or after formaldehyde treatment to eliminate the action of any possible interfering substances (Section IB).

(5) Similar results were also obtained with alcoholic and ethereal extracts of germinated *mung* and of the Indian fruit *bel* (Sections V and VI).

(6) By heating an alcoholic extract of cabbage at 36° for one hour a progressive increase in ascorbic acid throughout the period was observed (Section IX).

(7) There is a considerable difference in the ascorbic acid values obtained after treatment with hydrogen sulphide in the hot and in the cold conditions. This can hardly be explained on the oxidase theory, as all the dehydroascorbic acid formed would be readily reduced by sulphuretted hydrogen in the cold, and the increased value of ascorbic acid after hot treatment with sulphuretted hydrogen has therefore apparently been produced by heat. This effect is observed not only with suspensions of cabbage in water, where it may be argued that a larger quantity of ascorbic acid has been liberated by greater disintegration of the cabbage substance by heat, but also with aqueous and alcoholic extracts of cabbage, where no such explanation can be valid.

Not only has thus the existence of combined ascorbic acid in these materials been demonstrated, but, as has been shown in Section III, by treatment of cabbage with dry ether it has been possible to extract ascorbigen from cabbage in a state practically free from ascorbic acid. Further studies are proceeding on the nature of ascorbigen.

As has been shown in Section VII, the alcoholic extract of ripe or green mango does not contain any ascorbigen. It would thus seem that not all plant foodstuffs contain ascorbigen.

As shown in Section VIII, in a 0.2% acid solution (with HCl) of cabbage extracts there is a considerable splitting up of ascorbigen in one hour at room temperature. It would seem, therefore, that ascorbigen solutions would undergo similar splitting up by gastric juice in the stomach.

C O N C L U S I O N.

Working with alcoholic and ethereal extracts of cabbage, germinated *kancha mung* (*Phaseolus mungo*) and the Indian fruit *bel* (*Aegle marmelos*), it has been demonstrated that the increase of ascorbic acid value, which these extracts undergo on heating, cannot be due to the destruction of ascorbic acid oxidase but is to be ascribed to the presence of some ascorbic acid in a combined form. It is proposed to call this combined ascorbic acid "ascorbigen".

Ether has been found to be able to extract ascorbigen from cabbage in a state practically free from ascorbic acid. Ascorbigen solutions obtained from cabbage undergo splitting in 0.2 per cent acid solution (with HCl) at room temperature. Ripe and green mangoes have been found to be free from ascorbigen.

INDIAN INSTITUTE FOR MEDICAL RESEARCH,
CALCUTTA, AND
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE, CALCUTTA.

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